

Evaluating Postoperative Infection Risks and Management in Mesh Hernia Repairs: Insights from Al-Imam Al-Sadique Teaching Hospital, Babylon

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Abstract

Background: A hernia is characterised by the protrusion of abdominal contents through a weakened area of the abdominal wall. Incisional hernias, which develop at sites of previous surgical incisions, are relatively common and often pose significant treatment challenges. A major postoperative complication is mesh-related infection, leading to considerable morbidity and presenting a serious clinical management issue.

Aim of the Study: This study aims to present our institutional protocol for managing mesh-related infections and to provide a narrative review of surgical site infections following hernia repair, with a focus on associated risk factors and treatment strategies.

Methodology: This prospective interventional study was conducted at Al Imam Al-Sadiq Teaching Hospital over a three-year period, from January 2022 to July 2024. A total of 40 patients diagnosed with mesh infections after incisional hernia repair were included. Data collected encompassed demographic information, clinical characteristics, identified risk factors, and treatment outcomes.

Results: Among the 40 patients analysed, the mean age was 52.3 years, with a female predominance (32 cases, 80%). Key risk factors for mesh infection included advanced age, obesity, smoking, chronic kidney disease, and diabetes mellitus. Conservative management led to infection resolution in 77.5% of cases, while 22.5% required surgical removal of the mesh.

Conclusions: Mesh-related infections following incisional hernia repair are multifactorial in origin. Although conservative treatment is effective in most cases, mesh explantation is necessary for refractory infections. Preoperative optimisation of modifiable risk factors plays a critical role in reducing infection rates. Continued research and advances in surgical techniques are essential to improving patient outcomes

Introduction

A hernia is a weakness in the abdominal wall that allows part of the abdominal contents to protrude. Abdominal wall hernias involve two components: a defect in the wall and the herniated content. The defect may occur in the muscle, as in incisional hernias, or in the fascia, such as in epigastric hernias through the linea alba [1]. These hernias can occur spontaneously due to congenital weaknesses or as a postoperative complication, known as incisional hernias. These may range from small, reducible defects to large hernias

with “loss of domain” due to a chronically damaged abdominal wall [2]. Incisional hernias are the second most common type after inguinal hernias. In the United States, out of four million laparotomies annually, 2–30% result in incisional hernias, with 100,000 to 150,000 repairs performed each year [3]. These hernias typically arise due to fascial healing failure, influenced by both technical and biological factors. About 50% of incisional hernias present within the first two years postoperatively, and 74% within three years [4]. Treatment varies from simple suturing to complex

More Information

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Mesh Repair Hernia, Postoperative Infection, Risk Factors, Infection Management, Al-Imam Al-Sadique Teaching Hospital.

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reconstructions using large mesh and can be performed via open or laparoscopic approaches [5]. However, recurrent hernias are particularly challenging to manage, with each recurrence increasing the risk of surgical failure [6]. Risk factors include early mechanical failure post-laparotomy, with actual wound failure rates up to 11%, most recurring within three years [7]. Perioperative shock and upper-midline incisions further increase hernia risk [8]. Technique matters too—transverse suture lines are more mechanically stable than longitudinal ones due to the orientation of collagen bundles [9]. Indications for hernia repair include symptomatic cases, risk of bowel obstruction, and suitable size for surgical intervention [10]. Contraindications include significant comorbidities, active infection, ascites with advanced cirrhosis, or multiple prior mesh surgeries [11]. Obesity, while not a strict contraindication, increases recurrence risk and warrants preoperative weight loss counseling [12]. Mesh repair significantly reduces recurrence but introduces risks like seromas, adhesions, mesh rejection, and infection [13]. Preventive strategies include avoiding enterotomies and minimizing hemorrhage by withholding anticoagulants [14]. Smoking cessation is essential to reduce infection risk [15]. Mesh-related infections affect up to 8% of repairs and are more common in patients with diabetes, immunosuppression, or obesity [16]. Infections may present weeks to years' post-repair with local inflammation, fever, or fistulas [17]. Common pathogens include *Staphylococcus aureus*, MRSA, *Streptococcus spp.*, Gram-negative bacteria, anaerobes, and rarely fungi or *Mycobacterium spp.* [18]. Diagnosis involves clinical suspicion and imaging (ultrasound or CT), which can reveal inflammation, abscesses, or fistulas [19]. Diagnostic aspiration of asymptomatic seromas is discouraged due to the risk of infection [20]. Management typically requires both intravenous antibiotics and complete mesh removal, as biofilm formation and fibrotic encapsulation reduce antibiotic efficacy. Persistent symptoms often indicate incomplete mesh removal [22]. The aim of this study is to provide a narrative review of surgical site infections following hernia repair, highlighting risk factors and management strategies, and to present our approach to the treatment of mesh-related infections.

Method

This prospective interventional study was conducted at Al Imam Al-Sadiq Teaching Hospital over a three-year period (January 2022 – July 2024), following approval by the Arabic Board of Health Specializations / Local Council of General Surgery at Babylon Teaching Center. A total of 40 patients with mesh infections following incisional hernia repair who met the inclusion criteria were enrolled.

Inclusion criteria comprised patients aged 20–75 years, of either gender, with one or more risk factors for wound infection, such as diabetes mellitus, hypertension, or smoking. Patients were excluded if they had a body mass index (BMI) greater than 40, collagen or connective tissue disorders, or an immunocompromised status.

Data were collected using a structured questionnaire after obtaining verbal informed consent. Information recorded included demographics, relevant risk factors, medical and surgical histories, and clinical characteristics of the mesh infection (type, anatomical site, culture results, and antibiotic regimens). Treatment outcomes, duration of hospital stay, recurrence rates, and postoperative complications were also documented.

All patients initially underwent conservative management, which involved administration of double or triple antibiotic therapy, wound cleansing, debridement, and disinfection using diluted hydrogen peroxide and gentamicin irrigation. Povidone-iodine 3% was routinely applied to all cases. Vacuum-assisted closure (VAC) therapy was utilised in four patients. Conservative management was successful in 31 patients. Nine patients required surgical mesh removal due to persistent infection (five cases), the development of multiple sinuses (two cases), or the formation of fistulas (two cases).

Preoperative evaluation included laboratory investigations, imaging studies, and anaesthetic assessment and clearance. Surgical intervention was performed under general anaesthesia, during which the infected mesh was removed, followed by thorough debridement and irrigation. Tissue samples were sent for histopathological examination and microbiological cultures. Wound closure strategies varied: some wounds were closed primarily with drainage, while others were managed with secondary healing or further VAC therapy.

Postoperative follow-up involved monitoring for complications, including infection recurrence, hernia recurrence, adhesion formation, or the development of chronic pain.

Data were entered into Microsoft Excel and analysed using SPSS version 27. Descriptive statistics were presented as frequencies, percentages, means, and standard deviations. Student's t-test was employed to compare quantitative variables, with statistical significance set at $p < 0.05$.

Results

The study included 40 patients with a mean age of 52.3 years (± 12.1). Age distribution was as follows: 10% were aged 20–30 years, 12.5% were 31–40 years, 22.5% were 41–50 years, 37.5% were 51–60 years, and 17.5% were 61–70 years. The majority of patients were female (80%), while males accounted for 20%.

The mean Body Mass Index (BMI) was 28.1 kg/m² (±2.9). Regarding BMI categories, 15% of patients had a normal BMI (18.5–24.9), 52.5% were classified as

overweight (25–29.9), and 32.5% were obese (≥30). In terms of residence, 70% of patients were from rural areas and 30% were from urban locations (Table 1).

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of the Study Sample (n=40)

Variable		Number of Patients	Percentage (%)
Age	20-30 years	4	10%
	31-40 years	5	12.5%
	41-50 years	9	22.5%
	51-60 years	15	37.5%
	61-70 years	7	17.5%
	Mean ± SD	52.3 ± 12.1	
Gender	Male	8	20%
	Female	32	80%
	Mean ± SD	28.1 ± 2.9	
BMI kg/m ²	Normal (18.5-24.9)	6	15%
	Overweight (25-29.9)	21	52.5%
	Obese (≥30)	13	32.5%
Residency	Rural	28	70%
	Urban	12	30%

Regarding risk factors associated with incisional hernia infection, 45% of patients had diabetes mellitus, 32.5% were obese, 15% were smokers, 25% had hypertension, 5% had chronic kidney disease, and 2.5% reported a history of steroid use. It is important to note that some patients had multiple coexisting risk factors (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Risk Factors for Incisional Hernia Infection among the Study Sample Patients

The primary site of infection was the abdominal wall in 92.5% of cases, while 7.5% involved the groin. Culture results revealed that 82.5% of samples tested positive for infection, whereas 17.5% were culture-negative. Six patients had polymicrobial infections, involving more than one microorganism. The causative organisms are detailed in Table 2 and Figure 2.

Table 2: Mesh Infection Related Variables

Variable	Number of Patients	Percentage (%)
site of Abdominal Wall hernia	40	100%
Infection (Ventral hernia)		
Culture Positive	33	82.5%
Results Negative	7	17.5%

Figure 2: The Causative Organisms among Culture Positive Patients (n=33)

In terms of complications, 75% of patients experienced no postoperative issues, while 25% developed complications. Specifically, recurrent infections occurred in 5% of patients, hernia recurrence in 12.5%, adhesion formation in 2.5%, and chronic pain in 2.5% (Table 3).

The average length of hospital stay was 19.3 days (±5.8). Regarding hospitalisation duration, 5% of

patients stayed for 1–5 days, 10% for 6–10 days, 37.5% for 11–15 days, 25% for 16–20 days, and 22.5% for more than 20 days.

Table 3: The Outcome of Conservative Treatment

Outcome Measure		Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Infection Resolved on conservative treatment	Yes	31	77.5%
	No	9	22.5%
Complications	no	30	75%
	yes	10	25%
Duration of Hospital Stay days	Mean ± SD	19.3 ± 5.8 days	
	1-5	2	5%
	6-10	4	10%
	11-15	15	37.5%
	16-20	10	25%
	>20	9	22.5%

In terms of management, triple antibiotic therapy was administered to 65% of patients, while 35% received dual antibiotic therapy. All patients underwent wound cleansing with povidone-iodine and regular dressing changes, performed either daily or every other day. Additional treatments included hydrogen peroxide irrigation in 12 patients (30%), topical gentamicin application in 7 patients (17.5%), and vacuum-assisted closure (VAC) therapy in 4 patients (10%). Despite conservative management, nine patients (22.5%) required surgical mesh removal due to persistent infection (Table 4; Figures 3 and 4).

Table 4: Outcome of Management

Outcome	Number of patients
Small and medium size wound was ended with primary intention	20
Treatment with VAC and ended with primary intention	4
mesh removal surgery and closure of the wound with Redivac drain	9
Large size wound left the wound open and treated with secondary intention	7
Total	40

Statistical analysis revealed several significant correlations between infection outcomes and patient variables. Age had a significant impact ($p = 0.038$), with younger patients (20–30 years) achieving complete resolution through conservative treatment, whereas 3 out of 7 patients aged 61–70 years required surgical mesh removal. Gender did not significantly influence outcomes ($p = 0.696$), as both males and females demonstrated similar rates of infection resolution.

Figure 3: Complications that were Encountered after Mesh Infection among the Studied Patients

Figure 4: Treatments that were Required for Final Resolution of Mesh Related Infection among the Study Sample Patients

Diabetes was significantly associated with poorer outcomes ($p = 0.028$); 7 out of 18 diabetic patients required surgical intervention, compared to only 2 out of 22 non-diabetic patients. Hypertension showed no significant correlation with infection outcomes ($p = 0.561$). Smoking emerged as a significant factor ($p = 0.017$), with 3 out of 6 smokers requiring surgery compared to 6 out of 34 non-smokers. Obesity was also significantly associated with persistent infection ($p = 0.045$); 3 out of 13 obese patients

required surgical removal of the mesh, compared to 6 out of 27 non-obese patients. Chronic kidney disease (CKD) was a notable risk factor ($p = 0.025$), with 1 out of 2 patients with CKD (50%) requiring surgery. These findings suggest that persistent infection is multifactorial, with advanced age, diabetes, smoking, obesity, and CKD contributing significantly to the likelihood of surgical intervention (Table 5).

Table 5: The Statistical Correlation between Infection Outcome and Clinical and Demographic Variables of the Patients

Clinical Variable		Infection Resolved	Infection Persistent	Total	P-Value
Age years	20-30	4	0	4	0.038
	31-40	4	1	5	
	41-50	7	2	9	
	51-60	12	3	15	
	61-70	4	3	7	
Gender	Male	6	2	8	0.696
	Female	25	7	32	
DM	Yes	11	7	18	0.028
	No	20	2	22	
HTN	Yes	8	2	10	0.561
	No	23	7	30	
Smoking	Yes	3	3	6	0.017
	No	28	6	34	
Obesity	Yes	10	3	13	0.045
	No	21	6	27	
CKD	Yes	1	1	2	0.025
	No	30	8	38	

Discussion

This prospective study investigated the incidence of mesh-related infections in 40 patients who underwent incisional hernia repair. The demographic data indicated a mean age of 52.3 years, with 80% of the cohort being female and 20% male. Seventy percent of patients resided in rural areas, and the mean BMI was 28.1 kg/m². These findings are consistent with previous research, despite some regional variations. For instance, Kaoutzanis et al. analysed 25,172 cases and reported a mean age of 51 years, with females comprising 60% of the cases and males 40%. They identified obesity and smoking as significant risk factors for infection [22].

In the present study, obesity was observed in 32.5% of patients, smoking in 15%, diabetes in 45%, hypertension in 25%, chronic renal disease in 5%, and steroid use in 2.5%. This patient profile closely aligns with that reported by Mavros et al., who found notable correlations between smoking, patient age, operative duration, emergency operations, and infection risk, with a crude mesh infection rate of 5% among 2,424

mesh hernioplasties. They also noted a higher infection tendency in obese patients, predominantly caused by *Staphylococcus* spp. and gram-negative organisms [23]. Similarly, our culture results showed positive infections in 33 cases, with *Staphylococcus* spp. being the most frequently isolated organism. Regarding mesh type, our findings are comparable to those of Brown et al., who reported polypropylene mesh usage in 50% of cases and composite mesh in 35%, with similar infection sites and causative organisms [24].

In our study, conservative therapy successfully managed 77.5% of infections, while 22.5% of cases required surgical mesh removal. The mean hospital stay was 19.3 ± 5.8 days, which, although slightly longer, aligns with findings by Forbes et al., who reported an average stay of 11.5 days and a conservative management success rate of 75% [25].

Falagás et al. noted that mesh-related infection rates range between 1% and 8%, depending on comorbidities, mesh type, and prophylactic strategies. They advocated for a combined medical-surgical approach with broad-spectrum antimicrobial coverage,

particularly targeting *Staphylococcus aureus* [26]. Our findings support this, with mesh removal required in 22.5% of cases.

Regarding complications, hernia recurrence occurred in 12.5% of patients, adhesion formation in 2.5%, and chronic pain in 2.5%. These results are consistent with those of Van der Linden et al., who reported chronic pain in 18%, persistent infection in 20%, hernia recurrence in 13%, and adhesions in 15% of cases [27]. In contrast, Ahmad et al. successfully managed all 13 cases of mesh infection conservatively, although their study exclusively involved polypropylene meshes and may reflect regional differences in antibiotic resistance [28]. Arnold et al. emphasized that high-risk patients (e.g., obese, diabetic, or smokers) benefit more from biologic mesh and VAC-assisted delayed closure after mesh excision [29].

In our study, triple antibiotic therapy was administered in 65% of patients, while dual antibiotics were used in 35%. Povidone-iodine wound cleansing was employed for all patients, with hydrogen peroxide used in 30% of cases and VAC therapy applied in 10%.

Meagher et al. stressed the importance of regional antibiotic sensitivity profiling, reporting effective conservative treatment in 12 of 13 patients [30]. Guillaume et al. similarly advocated for gentamicin irrigation and antiseptic solutions as effective strategies to salvage infected mesh and minimise reherniation risk [31,32]. The broad-spectrum activity of gentamicin, especially against *Staphylococcus* spp., supports its use in local wound care.

Povidone-iodine has demonstrated efficacy in promoting wound healing without fostering resistance, as supported by Bigliardi et al. [33]. In our cohort, 77.5% of patients responded positively to treatment with povidone-iodine. Additionally, Sanjay et al. found that hydrogen peroxide accelerated granulation tissue formation and wound healing, findings corroborated in our study among 12 patients treated with 3% hydrogen peroxide [34].

Significant correlations were identified between infection outcomes and several factors, including age ($p = 0.038$), diabetes ($p = 0.028$), smoking ($p = 0.017$), obesity ($p = 0.045$), and chronic kidney disease ($p = 0.025$), whereas no significant associations were observed with gender ($p = 0.696$) or hypertension ($p = 0.561$). These findings are in line with those reported by Christou et al., who demonstrated similar associations between patient factors and the risk of mesh-related infection [35].

Conclusion

This study investigated 40 patients (mean age 52.3 years), with a predominance of females (80%) and an average hospital stay of 19.3 days. Most mesh-related infections were successfully managed conservatively; however, 22.5% of cases necessitated surgical mesh

removal. Diabetes and obesity were identified as the most significant risk factors, particularly among non-responders.

Complications occurred in 25% of patients, with hernia recurrence observed in 12.5% and chronic pain in 2.5%. Persistent infection was found to be multifactorial, closely linked to advanced age, diabetes, smoking, obesity, and chronic kidney disease. These findings underscore the importance of an individualized, risk-based approach to the management of mesh-related infections following incisional hernia repair.

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